

Karnataka because of their wide distribution during kharif.

Each test variety was surrounded by highly susceptible varieties HR-12 for BL, Binnibhog for BS, and PTB20 for UDb to expose them to natural infection. Observations were recorded using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. BL and BS were rated by lesion type and percent leaf area affected. Blast incidence after flowering was recorded as percent neck infection, and number of discolored grains per panicle was recorded for GD assessment. Percent infected panicles was recorded for UDb.

KMS7, KMS9, KMS5914, KMP10, KMP39, KMP41, and Jaya had resistant reactions to the four diseases (see table). □

TABLE CONTINUED

Variety	Disease score ^a				
	BL		BS	GD	UDb
	Leaf	Neck			
29509	R	M	M	M	S
KMP101	R	R	M	R	R
Pusa 150	R	R	R	R	M
KMP10	R	R	R	R	R
29781	M	M	R	R	M
HP-1-1	R	R	R	M	M
KMP41	R	R	R	R	R
KMS5914	R	R	R	R	R
KMP39	R	R	R	R	R
ES-18	M	M	M	R	S
Jaya	R	R	R	R	R
IR20	R	R	M	R	R
Rasi	R	M	M	R	M
Mangala	R	R	M	R	M
IR32	M	R	M	R	R

^aR = resistant (0-3 of the 1980 SES scale), M = moderately susceptible (4-6) and, S = susceptible (7-9).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Evaluation of promising gall midge-resistant cultivars

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood Mason) Mani is a major pest of rice in kharif in many Indian rice growing states. Thirty-eight promising gall midge resistant cultivars developed by breeders were received through the All-India Coordina-

ted Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, during 1979 kharif for testing at the Central Rice Research Institute, Orissa. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications. Seedlings were spaced at 20 × 15 cm and the plot was fertilized with 60 kg N, 22 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha. Silvershoots were counted at 30 and 50 days after transplanting and average incidence was calculated.

The maximum 32.6% silvershoots was recorded for WGL 26888

(IR22/W12708). Eight cultivars had less than 3% silvershoots, which was significant at the 1% level. They were OR140-9-3 (CR94/RPW6-13), OR158-7-1 (GMR15 18/Pankaj), WGL 26450, WGL 26528, WGL 26536, WGL 26591, WGL 26965, and WGL 27015 (Surekha/Kakatiya). Of these, OR140-9-3, OR158-7-1, and WGL 26450 also had less than 2% silvershoots at Raipur, Rudrur, Bhubaneswar, Mangalore, and Warangal. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought tolerance

Screening wetland rice varieties for drought tolerance

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Drought tolerance at vegetative stage is desirable for deepwater rice. Forty varieties (10 recommended, 11 traditional, and 16 improved) including 2 drought-resistant and 1 susceptible check were

Comparative performance^a of some wetland rice varieties under drought stress.

Entry	Initial stand establishment, 21 DS	Drought tolerance, 45 DS	Recovery, 81 DS	Height (cm), 133 DS	Phenotypic acceptability 133 DS
<i>Recommended varieties</i>					
Pankaj	8.3	9	7.6	31.1	8.3
Mahsuri	7.3	9	8.3	49.3	8.3
Swarna (IET 5656)	9	9	9	22.6	8.3
CR 1009	7.6	9	7.6	49.2	7.6
CR1014	7	9	7.6	61.1	7.6
BIET 821	3.6	3.6	5	88	5
<i>Traditional indica</i>					
OC1393	6.3	7.6	6.3	71.3	7
NC487/77	1.6	1	1.6	93.6	1

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